

Facilitators and barriers in accessing palliative care Services in Low-and-Middle-Income Countries A Systematic Review

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Background

56.8M

people need palliative care each year (most in LMICs)

Access Gap

14%
receive needed palliative care

Access gap

Children – 98% in LMICs, almost half in Africa

Research Gap

90% of QI/POM research in high-income countries
(Peeler et al., 2025).

- Need for patient and caregiver perspectives
- Gaps in existing reviews on qualitative data

Objectives

- Synthesize qualitative evidence on barriers and facilitators
- Identify key themes from diverse LMIC contexts
- Assess data quality using JBI critical appraisal tool

Methodology

- Systematic review (PROSPERO registered)
- Databases: PubMed, ClinicalKey, Google Scholar
- PRISMA guidelines followed
- Inclusion: Qualitative studies from LMICs

Article screening

Included:

- Qualitative studies
- Conducted in LMICs
- English language

Excluded:

- Quantitative only
- High-income country settings
- Non-English or incomplete reports

Results

- 15 studies across Asia(8) and Africa(7)

Highlighted Countries - South & Southeast Asia

Highlighted Countries - Sub-Saharan Africa

Results cnt.

- Populations: Patients, caregivers, providers, policy makers
- Diverse sample sizes
- Contexts

Name	Country	Study Population	Year	Barriers Identified	Facilitators Identified	Key Themes
Barriers and facilitators to the implementation of palliative care services at five tertiary hospitals	Nigeria	Patients, caregivers, healthcare providers	2025	Financial constraints, late referrals, provider shortage, substandard opioids, poor knowledge and beliefs	Positive provider attitudes, training interest, patient demand	CFIR: Innovation, Outer/Inner Setting, Individuals, Implementation Process
Determinants of access and utilization of cervical cancer treatment and palliative care services	Zimbabwe	Healthy women, cervical cancer patients, health workers	2019	Centralized services, cost, poor referral systems, staff shortages, lack of follow-up	Improved screening awareness, integration with HIV services	Health system, societal, individual
Expectations and barriers to the utilization of specialist palliative care services	Ghana	Cancer patients in tertiary facility	2023	Financial constraints, poor referrals, long distances, poor awareness of services	Desire for involvement in decision-making, meaningful communication	Expectations, structural barriers, communication gaps
Find Out What They Lack, Try to Provide	India	Patients, caregivers, clinicians, staff at Pallium India	2019	Poor healthcare infrastructure, poverty, limited opioid access, lack of trained clinicians	Community-based care, holistic model, volunteer engagement, flexible care delivery	People-centered care, accessibility, holistic support, structural adaptation
Exploring Supportive Care for Very Severe COPD in Malaysia	Malaysia	Patients with severe COPD, HCPs, policymakers	2025	Poor understanding of palliative care for COPD, lack of coordinated services, cultural taboos	Interest in raising awareness, stakeholder engagement, recognition of cultural context	Disease invisibility, psychosocial suffering, cultural influence, system gaps

Author	Country	Study Population	Year	Barriers Identified	Facilitators Identified	Key Themes
Mind the Gaps: Challenges for Cervical Cancer Care in Uganda	Uganda	Healthcare professionals in gynecology and screening units	2013	Lack of awareness, provider knowledge gaps, lack of transport, limited screening facilities, delayed diagnosis	Health worker commitment, visual inspection methods (VIA/VILI)	Multilevel barriers, human resource limitations, systemic delays, late presentation
Healthcare professionals' views on how palliative care should be delivered in Bhutan	Bhutan	Healthcare professionals in Bhutan	2021	Cultural taboos about death, lack of trained personnel, resource scarcity, lack of standard guidelines	Willingness to integrate spiritual care, community involvement, interest in capacity building	Holistic care, system strengthening, culturally sensitive delivery, role clarity
HIV in resource-limiting settings: Palliative care barriers	Multiple LMICs	HIV-positive patients, care providers	2022	Stigma, lack of trained providers, limited opioid access, policy neglect, competing healthcare priorities	Integration with HIV services, task shifting, donor funding for HIV programs	Health system integration, stigma reduction, policy advocacy
Barriers and facilitators in COPD palliative care delivery in Malaysia	Malaysia	Patients with COPD, caregivers, healthcare providers	2023	Lack of awareness about palliative care for non-cancer patients, fragmentation of services, stigma	Stakeholder support, guideline development, patient-centered goals	Service integration, awareness gaps, guideline-based care
Utilizing intricate care networks: An ethnography in Indonesia	Indonesia	Patients, family caregivers, and health professionals (n=49)	2025	Lack of professional palliative care, limited awareness, fragmented services, absence of structured home care	Community networks, spiritual care, complementary medicine, compassionate care culture	Creative navigation, community cooperation, cultural sensitivity, gaps in formal services

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Views and experiences of opioid access in a low-resource setting	India	Palliative care providers and public representatives	2023	Stigma, lack of training, regulatory fears, misconceptions about addiction	Positive experiential learning, State policy in Kerala, supportive community services	Training needs, policy-driven equity, experiential attitude shifts
Palliative Care Challenges in Nigeria: A qualitative study of interprofessional perceptions	Nigeria	Doctors, nurses, and allied health professionals	2023	Resource scarcity, limited trained personnel, inconsistent opioid supply, low prioritization	Collaborative teamwork, targeted training, advocacy by specialists	Capacity gaps, systemic neglect, importance of interprofessional synergy
Mind the gaps: Uganda's palliative care services	Uganda	Patients, caregivers, health providers	2020	Geographical challenges, underfunding, weak referral systems	Community outreach, integration with HIV programs, NGO support	Service accessibility, role of NGOs, need for structural strengthening
Perceptions of palliative care in a lower middle-income Muslim country	Pakistan	Patients, caregivers, religious leaders	2022	Cultural taboos, religious misconceptions, lack of structured services	Faith-based acceptance, clergy involvement, community volunteerism	Spiritual care integration, religious literacy, culturally responsive care
Palliative care for pediatric cancer patients at Bugando Medical Center	Tanzania	Pediatric cancer patients, caregivers, providers	2021	Delayed referrals, limited pediatric palliative services, financial burden	NGO funding, motivated staff, caregiver resilience	Pediatric care gaps, caregiver-centered strategies, importance of early integration

Summary of barriers, facilitators and themes identified

Barriers

1. **Health system gaps-** infrastructure, staff, referrals, guidelines
2. **Access and resources-** finance, poverty, opioids, distance
3. **Knowledge & awareness-** training gaps, cultural taboos,
4. **Cultural stigma-** stigma, low prioritization

Facilitators

1. **Positive attitude –** Provider willingness, demand, resilience
2. **Community engagement –** NGOs, volunteerism, community-based care models
3. **Stakeholder involvement -** HIV programs, team work, advocacy, **Policy** State policies, training, guidelines

Themes identified

1. Health system readiness
2. Societal & Cultural influence
3. Individual level factors

Risk of Bias (JBI Checklist)

- Most studies scored 7–10/10
- High quality of congruity and ethical clarity

No.	First Author (Year)	Total Yes	Overall Risk of Bias	Congruity: Philosophy and Methodology	Congruity: Methodology & Research Q.	Congruity: Methodology & Data Collection	Congruity: Methodology & Analysis	Congruity: Methodology & Interpretation	Locating Researcher Culturally/Theoretically	Researcher Influence on Research	Participant Representation	Ethical Approval	Analysis & Interpretation Representation
1	Bayuo (2021)	9	Low	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Unclear	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
2	Chukwuneke (2021)	8	Moderate	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	Unclear	Yes	Yes
3	Namukwaya (2021)	10	Low	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
4	Bhujun (2021)	10	Low	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
5	Shanmugavadivel (2020)	9	Low	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Unclear	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
6	Ramasamy (2021)	9	Low	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Unclear	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
7	Namukwaya (2021b)	10	Low	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
8	Shalei (2021)	9	Low	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Unclear	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes

Conclusion

Access to palliative care in LMICs can be improved by addressing system gaps, raising awareness, decentralizing services, and promoting culturally sensitive, community-based care models.

Thank you